

On Neutrosophic Vague Binary $BZMV^{dM}$ Sub - algebra of $BZMV^{dM}$ - algebra In Neutrosophic Vague Binary Sets

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Abstract: In Model theory, common algebraic structures found are Lattices and Boolean Algebras. In the broad field of research, various algebraic structures can be introduced for a set. BCK, BCI, BCH, BH etc. are some of them. In this paper, a comparatively novel mixed structure namely, de Morgan $BZMV$ – algebra, is presented for neutrosophic vague binary sets. Obviously, this is a mixed output pattern and more effective than the already existing single output approaches. Instead of our usual Boolean approach, this model is a kind of de Morgan lattice extension. Additionally, it takes the effects of Lukasiewicz many- valued logic, combined with BZ –lattices. The logical connective operators, MV conjunction operator \odot and MV disjunction operator \oplus have shown the behavior of idempotency, as same as, their underlying logical patterns, framed of ‘usual conjunction \wedge and disjunction \vee ’. Both kind of orthocomplementations or negations, one as a fuzzy type and other one as an intuitionistic type are implemented by BZ lattices. That is, Kleene (fuzzy or Zadeh) orthocomplementation \neg and Brouwer orthocomplementation \sim are got implemented in BZ - structure. Here \neg is a fuzzy type negation and \sim is an intuitionistic type negation. In our new type, de Morgan effects are given to these orthocomplementations and hence in this paper, instead of usual negations, de Morgan negations or orthocomplementations are used. Some ideals for this new concept have also got constructed. Behaviour of its direct sum, properties and some of its related theorems are also mentioned in this paper.

Keywords: vague $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, neutrosophic $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra , neutrosophic vague $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, prime ideal of $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, normal ideal of $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, \sim ideal of $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra, direct sum of neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra

Notations: $NVBS$ - neutrosophic vague binary set, $NVBSS$ - neutrosophic vague binary subset, $NVBI$ - neutrosophic vague binary ideal. Throughout this paper NVB indicates neutrosophic vague binary, NV denotes neutrosophic vague, N denotes neutrosophic and V denote vague

1. Introduction

For a set, different kinds of structures can be defined. Poset or partially ordered set is one such! In a poset, elements may or may not be comparable. (P, \leq) is a poset indicated by a relation \leq defined on P and does not give any sense to the actual meaning of ‘less than or equal to’. Chang [4] invented MV (Many – Valued) – algebra in 1958. As algebraic semantics of Lukasiewicz

many-valued (or multi-valued) logic, MV-algebra is considered to be an algebraic system with one binary operation, 2 unary operations and with one constant which satisfy certain axioms. In 1994, Vijay K. Khanna [24] explored lattices and Boolean algebra in his book. In 2010, N.O. Alshehri [1] introduced a new concept called an additive derivation of MV – algebra and investigated its several properties. It is possible to introduce a lattice structure from any MV – algebra. In 2017, Jean B. Nganou [13] introduced Stone MV – algebras and strongly complete MV – algebras. In 2008, Shokoofeh Ghorbani, Hasankhani. A and Esfandiar Eslami [23] introduced hyper MV – algebras. In 2012, Musa Hasankhani. M and Borumand Saeid. A [21] studied, hyper MV – algebras defined by bipolar-valued fuzzy sets. In 2014, Yongwei Yang, Xiaolong Xin and Pengfei He [28] gave some characterizations of MV – Algebras based on the theory of falling shadows. In 2003, Gianpiero Cattaneo and David Ciucci [11] gave an algebraic approach to shadowed sets. In 2003, Gianpiero Cattaneo and David Ciucci [12] also discussed on shadowed sets and related algebraic structures. In 2004, Cattaneo. G, Ciucci.D, Giuntini. R and Konig. M [3] discussed on algebraic structures related to many valued logical systems. In 1984, Komori. Y [15] introduced the concept of a BCC algebra. In 2018, Mozahir Anwar and Jay Nandan Prasad Singh [20] discussed on the direct sum of BCC algebra. In 1991, Ye. R. F [27] discussed on BZ-algebras. Several authors like Zhang. X. H in Korea and China termed weak BCC algebra as BZ algebra. In 2003, Xiaohong Zhang, Yongquan Wang and Wieslaw. A. Dudek [26] studied T-ideals in BZ (Brower – Zadeh) -algebras and T-type BZ-algebras. In 2009, Wieslaw A. Dudek, Xiaohong Zhang, Yongquan Wang [25] gave a study on ideals and atoms of BZ Algebras. In 2017, Yousefi. A and Borumand.Saeid. A [29] discussed on various types of ideals in $BZMV^{dM}$ -algebra. In 2020, Mohamed Abdel-Basset, Abdullallah Gamal, Le Hoang Son and Florentin Smarandache [16] provided a new approach for professional selection using bipolar neutrosophic multi criteria decision making method. In 2020, Mohamed Abdel – Basset, Weiping Ding, Rehab Mohamed and Noura Metawa [17] explained a new plithogenic Multicriteria approach, which is beneficial to the manufacturing industries, for evaluation of financial performance. For smart product service systems, in 2020, Mohamed Abdel-Basst, Rehab Mohamed, Mohamed Elhoseny [18] discussed on a novel framework to evaluate innovative value proposition. In 2020, Mohamed Abdel-Basset, Rehab Mohamed, Abd El-Nasser, H. Zaied, Abdullallah Gamal, Florentin Smarandache [19] developed a plithogenic model based on best – worst method in supply chain problem.

Heyting Algebra is introduced by a dutch mathematician and logician, Arend Heyting [29] in 1930, to formulize intuitionistic logic. Wajesberg algebra is introduced in 1984 by Joseph. Maria Font, Antonio. J. Rodriguez, Antonio Torrens [14] and it is an extension of BCK algebras. Ortho-algebra is introduced by Foulis, D. P, Greechie. R. J and Rüttimann. G. T [5] in the year 1992. An effect algebra is considered as a generalization of ortho-algebra. MV – algebra too, is a generalization of ortho- algebra. Effect algebra, which is a tool for the studies of unsharp elements in quantum mechanics, is introduced by Foulis. D. J and Bennett. M.K [6] in 1994. A special example for MV – algebra is effect algebra. An orthogonal algebra is an effect algebra. Heyting Wajesberg algebra is introduced by Gianpiero Cattaneo and Davide Ciucci [11] in the year 2002. Sometimes, HW algebra is called as pseudo Boolean algebra or even Brower Lattice. Boolean algebra, which is a generalization of power set algebra, is considered to be a complemented distributed lattice in an abstract algebra.

In 1999, G. Cattaneo, R. Giuntini, R. Pilla [2] introduced $BZMV^{dM}$ -algebra. It is an algebraic structure with a binary operation \oplus (which is both commutative and associative), with 2 unary operations \neg (Kleene orthocomplementation) and \sim (Brouwer orthocomplementation) and with two constants 0 and 1, satisfying certain axioms. \sim is also known as intuitionistic complement, since neither excluded middle law, $(a \vee \neg a = 0)$ nor double negation law, $(\neg \neg a = a)$ got satisfied by it, but it behaves well with non – contradiction law, $(a \wedge \neg a = 0)$. Any brouwer distributive lattice (resp. de Morgan Brouwer distributive lattice) becomes pre –brouwer distributive lattice (resp. de

Morgan pre - Brouwer distributive lattice), if it satisfies additionally the above non – contradiction law. So any Brouwer lattice is pre –Brouwer but the converse does not hold, generally. An open problem is given in paper [2] which rightly points towards the behavioral difference between MV – algebras and BZMV^{dm}-algebras. [0, 1] is an example for a BZMV^{dm}-algebra but it is not a MVBZ³ – algebra. Every equation which holds in every MV – algebra based on [0, 1] holds in every MV – algebra. But the open problem is that it is not known still, whether it is true for BZMV^{dm}-algebras. But it is true for every MVBZ³- algebra and the concrete MVBZ³- algebra based on $\{0, (\frac{1}{2}), 1\}$, that is, shadowed sets. Any stonian MV-algebra will act as a BZMV^{dm}-algebra and vice versa.

In 1993, Gau. W. L and Buehrer. D. J [9] introduced vague set theory. In 2005, Florentin Smarandache [8] introduced neutrosophic sets. In 2019, Emimancy. M and Francina Shalini. A [7] introduced Bipolar-valued fuzzy BZMV^{dm} sub- algebra. In 2019, Remya. P.B and Francina Shalini. A [22] developed neutrosophic vague binary sets. These sets are more useful than fuzzy, since neutrosophic criteria is implemented and it will provide three values for each data set values collected. Fuzzy sets limitation is got reduced in neutrosophic zone. In this paper, BZMV^{dm}-algebraic concepts are developed to neutrosophic vague binary sets. Ideals, direct sum, theorems are also got discussed to this novel concept.

In this paper the following points are newly presented

- \forall BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra for Different sets [Section 3]
 - ✓ \forall BZMV^{dm} Sub-algebra [Definition 3.1]
 - ✓ N BZMV^{dm} Sub-algebra [Definition 3.2]
 - ✓ NV BZMV^{dm} Sub-algebra [Definition 3.3]
- NVB BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra [Section 4]
 - ✓ NVB BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra [Definition 4.1]
- Ideal in Neutrosophic Vague Binary BZMV^{dm} Sub - algebra [Section 5]
 - ✓ NVB BZMV^{dm}- Ideal [Definition 5.1]
- Various Ideals in Neutrosophic Vague Binary BZMV^{dm}- subalgebra [Section 5]
 - ✓ Prime ideal, normal ideal, \sim ideal of NVB BZMV^{dm}-subalgebra [Definition 5.2]
- Direct sum of two NVB BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra [Section 6]

2. Preliminaries

In this section some preliminaries are given.

Definition 2.1 [22] (Neutrosophic vague binary set)

A neutrosophic vague binary set M_{NVB} (NVBS in short) over a common universe

$\{U_1 = \{x_j / 1 \leq j \leq n\}; U_2 = \{y_k / 1 \leq k \leq p\}\}$ is an object of the form

$$M_{NVB} = \left\{ \left\langle \frac{\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j), \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j), \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j)}{x_j}; \forall x_j \in U_1 \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k), \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k), \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k)}{y_k}; \forall y_k \in U_2 \right\rangle \right\}$$

is defined as

$$\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j) = [T^-(x_j), T^+(x_j)], \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j) = [I^-(x_j), I^+(x_j)] \text{ and } \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(x_j) = [F^-(x_j), F^+(x_j)]; x_j \in U_1 \text{ and}$$

$$\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k) = [T^-(y_k), T^+(y_k)], \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k) = [I^-(y_k), I^+(y_k)] \text{ and } \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(y_k) = [F^-(y_k), F^+(y_k)]; y_k \in U_2$$

where (1) $T^+(x_j) = 1 - F^-(x_j); F^+(x_j) = 1 - T^-(x_j); \forall x_j \in U_1$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 & T^+(y_k) = 1 - F^-(y_k); F^+(y_k) = 1 - T^-(y_k); \forall y_k \in U_2 \\
 (2) \quad & -0 \leq T^-(x_j) + I^-(x_j) + F^-(x_j) \leq 2^+; \quad -0 \leq T^-(y_k) + I^-(y_k) + F^-(y_k) \leq 2^+ \\
 & \text{or} \\
 & -0 \leq T^-(x_j) + I^-(x_j) + F^-(x_j) + T^-(y_k) + I^-(y_k) + F^-(y_k) \leq 4^+ \\
 & \text{and} \\
 & -0 \leq T^+(x_j) + I^+(x_j) + F^+(x_j) \leq 2^+; \quad -0 \leq T^+(y_k) + I^+(y_k) + F^+(y_k) \leq 2^+ \\
 & \text{or} \\
 & -0 \leq T^+(x_j) + I^+(x_j) + F^+(x_j) + T^+(y_k) + I^+(y_k) + F^+(y_k) \leq 4^+ \\
 (3) \quad & T^-(x_j), I^-(x_j), F^-(x_j) : V(U_1) \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ and } T^-(y_k), I^-(y_k), F^-(y_k) : V(U_2) \rightarrow [0, 1] \\
 & T^+(x_j), I^+(x_j), F^+(x_j) : V(U_1) \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ and } T^+(y_k), I^+(y_k), F^+(y_k) : V(U_2) \rightarrow [0, 1]
 \end{aligned}$$

Here $V(U_1), V(U_2)$ denotes power set of vague sets on U_1, U_2 respectively.

Definition 2.2 [24]

A poset (L, \leq) is said to form a lattice if for every $a, b \in L$, $\text{Sup } \{a, b\}$ and $\text{Inf } \{a, b\}$ exist in L . In that case, we write

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Sup } \{a, b\} &= (a \vee b) \quad [\text{read a join b}] \\
 \text{Inf } \{a, b\} &= (a \wedge b) \quad [\text{read a meet b}]
 \end{aligned}$$

Other notations like $(a + b)$ and $(a \cdot b)$ or $(a \cup b)$ and $(a \cap b)$ are also used for $\text{Sup } \{a, b\}$ & $\text{Inf } \{a, b\}$

Definition 2.3 [1] (MV- algebra)

An MV-algebra is a structure $(M, \oplus, *, 0)$ where \oplus is a binary operation, $*$ is a unary operation, and 0 is a constant such that the following axioms are satisfied for any $a, b \in M$:

- (MV1) $(M, \oplus, 0)$ is a commutative monoid
- (MV2) $(a^*)^* = a$
- (MV3) $(0^* \oplus a) = 0^*$
- (MV4) $(a^* \oplus b)^* \oplus b = (b^* \oplus a)^* \oplus a$

If we define the constant $1 = 0^*$ and the auxiliary operations \odot, \vee and \wedge by

$$a \odot b = (a^* \oplus b^*)^*, a \vee b = a \oplus (b \odot a^*), a \wedge b = a \odot (b \oplus a^*),$$

then $(M, \odot, 1)$ is a commutative monoid and the structure $(M, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ is a bounded distributive lattice. Also, we define the binary operation \ominus by $x \ominus y = x \odot y^*$. A subset X of an MV- algebra M is called sub algebra of M if and only if X is closed under the MV-operations defined in M . In any MV-algebras, one can define a partial order \leq by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x \wedge y = x$ for each $x, y \in M$. If the order relation \leq , defined over M , is total, then we say that M is linearly ordered. For an MV-algebra M , if we define $B(M) = \{x \in M : x \oplus x = x\} = \{x \in M : x \odot x = x\}$. Then, $(B(M), \oplus, *, 0)$ is both a largest subalgebra of M and a Boolean algebra

An MV-algebra M has the following properties for all $x, y, z \in M$,

- (1) $(x \oplus 1) = 1$
- (2) $(x \oplus x^*) = 1$
- (3) $(x \odot x^*) = 0$
- (4) If $(x \odot y) = 0$, then $x = y = 0$
- (5) If $(x \odot y) = 1$, then $x = y = 1$
- (6) If $x \leq y$, then $(x \vee z) \leq (y \vee z)$ and $(x \wedge z) \leq (y \wedge z)$
- (7) If $x \leq y$, then $(x \oplus z) \leq (y \oplus z)$ and $(x \odot z) \leq (y \odot z)$
- (8) $x \leq y$ if and only if $y^* \leq x^*$
- (9) $(x \oplus y) = y$ if and only if $(x \odot y) = x$

Definition 2.4 [20] (BZ-algebra)

An algebra $\langle X, *, 0 \rangle$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a BZ- algebra if it satisfies the following axioms :

For any $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $[(x * z) * (y * z)] * (x * y) = 0$
- (2) $(x * 0) = x$
- (3) $(x * y) = (y * x) = 0$ implies $x = y$

A partial ordering \leq can be defined by $x \leq y$ if and only if $(x * y) = 0$

Remark 2.5 [20]

A weak BCC algebra was also termed as BZ algebra in Korea and China by several authors e.g., X. H. Zhang.

Definition 2.6 [25, 26] (distributive Brouwer – Zadeh – lattice (BZ – lattice))

A distributive Brouwer - Zadeh (BZ)-lattice is a structure $\langle \Sigma, \vee, \wedge, \neg, \sim, 0 \rangle$, where

- (a) $\langle \Sigma, \vee, \wedge, 0 \rangle$ is a (nonempty) distributive lattice with minimum element 0
- (b) The mapping $\neg : \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$ is a Kleene orthocomplementation, that is
 - (doc-1) $\neg(\neg a) = a$
 - (doc-2) $\neg(a \vee b) = (\neg a \wedge \neg b)$
 - (re) $(a \wedge \neg a \leq b \vee \neg b)$
- (c) The mapping $\sim : \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$ is a Brouwer orthocomplementation, that is
 - (woc-1) $(a \wedge \sim \sim a) = a$
 - (woc-2) $\sim(a \vee b) = (\sim a \wedge \sim b)$
 - (woc-3) $(a \wedge \sim a) = 0$
- (d) The two orthocomplementations are linked by the following interconnection rule:
 - (in) $\neg \sim a = \sim \sim a$

The mapping \neg is also called the Lukasiewicz [or fuzzy (Zadeh)] orthocomplementation while the mapping \sim is an intuitionistic – like orthocomplementation. The element $1 := \sim 0 = \neg 0$ is the greatest element of Σ

Definition 2.7 [2] (distributive de Morgan BZ – lattice(BZ^{dm} – lattice))

A distributive de Morgan BZ -lattice (BZ^{dm} – lattice) is a distributive BZ- lattice for which the following hold : $\sim(a \wedge b) = (\sim a \vee \sim b)$

Definition 2.8 [11, 12] (Brouwer – Zadeh many – valued algebra (BZMV - algebra))

By pasting of BZ -lattices and MV – algebras one obtains so – called BZMV – algebra

A Brouwer Zadeh Many Valued (BZMV) algebra is a system $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \oplus, \neg, \sim, 0 \rangle$ where A is a non-empty set, 0 is a constant, \neg and \sim are unary operations, \oplus a binary operator, obeying the following axioms:

- (BZMV1) $(a \oplus b) \oplus c = (b \oplus c) \oplus a$
- (BZMV2) $(a \oplus 0) = a$
- (BZMV3) $\neg(\neg a) = a$
- (BZMV4) $\neg(\neg a \oplus b) \oplus b = \neg(a \oplus \neg b) \oplus a$
- (BZMV5) $\sim a \oplus \sim \sim a = \neg 0$
- (BZMV6) $a \oplus \sim \sim a = \sim \sim a$
- (BZMV7) $\sim \neg [(\neg(a \oplus \neg b) \oplus b)] = \neg(\sim \sim a \oplus \neg \sim \sim b) \oplus \neg \sim \sim b$

Definition 2.9 [2] (de Morgan BZMV (BZMV^{dm}) algebra

A de Morgan BZMV (BZMV^{dm}) algebra, is a BZMV algebra $\mathcal{A} = \langle A, \oplus, \neg, \sim, 0 \rangle$ where axiom (BZMV7) is replaced by the following:

$$(BZMV7') \sim \neg [(\neg (a \oplus \neg b) \oplus \neg b)] = \neg (\sim \sim a \oplus \neg \sim \sim b) \oplus \neg \sim \sim b$$

Connectives \vee and \wedge are the algebraic realization of logical disjunction and conjunction of a distributive lattice. In particular, they are idempotent operators. Connectives \oplus and \odot are the well known MV disjunction and MV conjunction operators, which are idempotent.

$$\begin{aligned} (a \odot b) &:= \neg (\neg a \oplus \neg b) \\ (a \vee b) &:= \neg (\neg a \oplus b) \oplus b \\ (a \wedge b) &:= \neg (a \oplus \neg b) \oplus \neg b \end{aligned}$$

A partial order can be naturally induced by the lattice operators as:

$$a \leq b \text{ iff } (a \wedge b) = a \text{ (equivalently, } a \vee b = b)$$

Let us notice that, since it is possible to prove that $\sim 0 = \neg 0$, in the sequel we set $1 := \sim 0 = \neg 0$

With respect to the just defined partial order we have that the lattice is bounded: $\forall a \in A, 0 \leq a \leq 1$

The unary operation $\neg : A \rightarrow A$ is a Kleene (or Zadeh) orthocomplementation (negation). In other words, it satisfies the properties:

- (K1) $\neg (\neg a) = a$
- (K2) $\neg (a \vee b) = \neg a \wedge \neg b$
- (K3) $a \wedge \neg a \leq b \vee \neg b$

Let us recall that under (K1), condition (K1), condition (K2) is equivalent to the dual de Morgan law. In general, neither the non-contradiction law,

$$\forall a : a \wedge \neg a = 0, \text{ nor the excluded middle law, } \forall a : a \vee \neg a = 1, \text{ are satisfied by this negation}$$

The unary operation $\sim : A \rightarrow A$ is a Brouwer orthocomplementation (negation). In other words, it satisfies the properties:

- (B1) $a \wedge \sim \sim a = a$ (equivalently, $a \leq \sim \sim a$)
- (B2) $\sim (a \vee b) = \sim a \wedge \sim b$
- (B3) $a \wedge \sim a = 0$

Remark 2.10 [29]

BZW and BZMV – algebras are equivalent structures.

Definition 2.11 [29] (Linear BZMV^{dm}-algebra)

In linear BZMV^{dm}-algebra A, Brouwer orthocomplementation \sim is uniquely defined in the following way for all $a \in A$.

$$\sim a = \begin{cases} 1 & ; \text{ if } a = 0 \\ 0 & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2.12 [9]

If A is a BZMV^{dm}-algebra then the following results are true:

- (1) $(u_x \oplus u_y) = (u_y \oplus u_x)$ (2) $(u_x \oplus u_y) \oplus u_z = u_x \oplus (u_y \oplus u_z)$ (3) $(u_x \oplus 1) = 1$
- (4) $(u_x \oplus \neg u_x) = 1$ (5) $\neg (u_x \oplus \sim \sim u_x) \oplus \sim \sim u_x = 1$ (6) $\neg u_x \oplus \sim \sim u_x = 1$
- (7) $u_x \wedge \sim \sim u_x = u_x$ (8) $\neg \sim u_x = \sim \sim u_x$ (9) $\sim (u_x \wedge u_y) = \sim u_x \vee \sim u_y$
- (10) $\sim (u_x \vee u_y) = \sim u_x \wedge \sim u_y$ (Equivalently, $u_x \leq u_y$ implies $\sim u_y \leq \sim u_x$)
- (11) $u_x \wedge \sim u_x = 0$ (12) $\sim u_x = \sim \sim \sim u_x$ (13) $\sim u_x \oplus \sim u_x = \sim u_x$ (14) $\neg 0 = \sim 0$

Definition 2.13 [29] (Ideal in BZMV^{dm}- algebra)

Let A be an BZMV^{dm}-algebra. An ideal of A is any subset I of A such that the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $0 \in I$ (ii) $x, y \in I$ imply $(x \oplus y) \in I$ (iii) $x \in I$ and $y \in A$ then $(x \odot y) \in I$

Definition 2.14 [29] (prime ideal of BZMV^{dm} algebra)

An ideal I is called a prime ideal if and only if $\forall x, y \in A, (x \odot \neg y) \in I$ or $(\neg x \odot y) \in I$

Definition 2.15 [29] (normal ideal of BZMV^{dm} algebra)

Let I be an ideal of A. I is called normal ideal whenever, $\forall x, y \in A, (\neg x \odot y) \in I$ if and only if $(\sim x \odot y \in I)$

Definition 2.16 [29] (~ ideal of BZMV^{dm} algebra)

Let A be a BZMV^{dm} – algebra. Let I be an ideal of A. Then it is called ~ ideal of A if it satisfies the following condition: $\forall x, y \in A$, if $(x \odot y) \in I$, then $(\sim \sim x \odot \sim \neg y \in I)$

Lemma 2.17 [21] (Fuzzy sub – hyper MV algebra)

A fuzzy subset μ of M is called a fuzzy sub-hyper-MV -algebra of M if it satisfies:

- 1) $(\forall x \in M), \mu(x) \leq \mu(x^*)$
- 2) $(\forall x, y \in M), \inf_{v \in x \oplus y} \mu(v) \geq \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}$

Definition 2.18 [7] (Bipolar valued fuzzy BZMV algebra)

Let $M = \langle M, \oplus, \neg, \sim, 0 \rangle$ be a BZMV – algebra with a non – empty set M, a binary operation \oplus , two unary operations \neg and \sim and with a constant 0. A bipolar valued fuzzy set $B = (\mu^-, \mu^+)$ is called bipolar valued fuzzy BZMV algebra of M, if for every x, y in M it satisfies:

- (1) $\mu^+(x) \leq \mu^+(\neg x)$ (2) $\mu^-(x) \geq \mu^+(\neg x)$ (3) $\mu^+(x) \leq \mu^+(\sim x)$ (4) $\mu^-(x) \geq \mu^+(\sim x)$
- (5) $\inf_{v \in x \oplus y} \mu^+(v) \geq \min \{ \mu^+(x), \mu^+(y) \}$ (6) $\sup_{v \in x \oplus y} \mu^-(v) \leq \max \{ \mu^-(x), \mu^-(y) \}$

3. BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra for different sets

In this section BZMV^{dm} algebraic structure is developed for vague and neutrosophic sets. Then it is extended to its hybrid set ‘neutrosophic vague’ with single universe.

Definition 3. 1 (Vague BZMV^{dm} Sub-algebra)

A vague BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra (V BZMV^{dm} - subalgebra, in short) is a structure $\mathfrak{M}_A = (\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_A}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ which satisfies, the following two \mathfrak{M}_A inequalities:

\mathfrak{M}_A inequality (1) : $\left(\inf_{v \in x \oplus y} V_A(v) \right) \geq r \min \{ V_A(x), V_A(y) \} ; \forall v, x, y \in \mathbf{U}$ i.e.,
 $\left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} t_A(v) \right) \geq \min \{ t_A(x), t_A(y) \} ; \left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} f_A(v) \right) \leq \max \{ f_A(x), f_A(y) \}$

\mathfrak{M}_A inequality (2) : (i) $V_A(x) \geq V_A(\neg x)$ i.e., $t_A(x) \geq t_A(\neg x)$ & $f_A(x) \leq f_A(\neg x)$

(ii) $V_A(x) \geq V_A(\sim x)$ i.e., $t_A(x) \geq t_A(\sim x)$ & $f_A(x) \leq f_A(\sim x)$

Here,

- A is a non- empty vague set with universe **U**
- $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_A} = (\mathbf{U}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ is a BZMV^{dm}– algebraic structure of the underlying universal set **U** of a vague set A, with a binary operation \oplus , two unary operations \neg, \sim and a constant 0 which satisfies the following BZMV^{dm} axioms : $\forall x, y, z \in \mathbf{U}$
 - (1) $(x \oplus y) \oplus z = (y \oplus z) \oplus x$ (2) $(x \oplus 0) = x$ (3) $\neg(\neg u_x) = u_x$
 - (4) $\neg(\neg x \oplus y) \oplus y = \neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus x$ (5) $\sim x \oplus \sim \sim x = \neg 0$ (6) $x \oplus \sim \sim x = \sim \sim x$
 - (7) $\sim \neg [(\neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y)] = \neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \oplus \neg \sim \sim y$

Definition 3.2 (Neutrosophic BZMV^{dm} sub algebra)

A neutrosophic **BZMV^{dm}**-subalgebra (**N BZMV^{dm}**-sub algebra, in short) is a structure $\mathfrak{M}_{M_N} = (\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_N}}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ which satisfies, the following two \mathfrak{M}_{M_N} inequalities:

\mathfrak{M}_{M_N} inequality (1):

$$\left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} N_{M_N}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \geq r \min \{N_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}), N_{M_N}(\mathbf{y})\}; \forall \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{U} \quad \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} T_{M_N}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \geq \min \{T_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}), T_{M_N}(\mathbf{y})\}; \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} I_{M_N}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \leq \max \{I_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}), I_{M_N}(\mathbf{y})\}; \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} F_{M_N}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \leq \max \{F_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}), F_{M_N}(\mathbf{y})\}$$

\mathfrak{M}_{M_N} inequality (2) :

- (i) $N_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \geq N_{M_N}(\neg \mathbf{x})$; i.e., $T_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \geq T_{M_N}(\neg \mathbf{x}); I_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \leq I_{M_N}(\neg \mathbf{x}); F_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \leq F_{M_N}(\neg \mathbf{x})$
- (ii) $N_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \geq N_{M_N}(\sim \mathbf{x})$; i.e., $T_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \geq T_{M_N}(\sim \mathbf{x}); I_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \leq I_{M_N}(\sim \mathbf{x}); F_{M_N}(\mathbf{x}) \leq F_{M_N}(\sim \mathbf{x})$

Here,

- M_N is a non- empty neutrosophic set with universe \mathbf{U}
- $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_N}} = (\mathbf{U}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ is a **BZMV^{dm}** – algebraic structure of the underlying universal set \mathbf{U} of a neutrosophic set M_N with a binary operation \oplus , two unary operations \neg, \sim and a constant $\mathbf{0}$ which satisfies the following **BZMV^{dm}** - axioms : $\forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{U}$

- (1) $(\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y}) \oplus \mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{y} \oplus \mathbf{z}) \oplus \mathbf{x}$ (2) $(\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{x}$ (3) $\neg(\neg \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}$
- (4) $\neg(\neg \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y}) \oplus \mathbf{y} = \neg(\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{y}) \oplus \mathbf{x}$ (5) $\sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x} = \neg \mathbf{0}$ (6) $\mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x} = \sim \sim \mathbf{x}$
- (7) $\sim \neg [(\neg(\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{y}) \oplus \neg \mathbf{y})] = \neg(\sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{y}) \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{y}$

Definition 3.3 (Neutrosophic Vague BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra)

A neutrosophic vague **BZMV^{dm}** – subalgebra (**NV BZMV^{dm}** sub algebra, in short) is a structure $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}} = (\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}}}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ with, $\hat{\mathbf{T}} = [\mathbf{T}^{-1}, \mathbf{T}^+]$; $\hat{\mathbf{I}} = [\mathbf{I}^{-1}, \mathbf{I}^+]$; $\hat{\mathbf{F}} = [\mathbf{F}^{-1}, \mathbf{F}^+]$, which satisfies, the following two $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}}$ inequalities:

$\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}}$ inequality (1) :

$$\left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} NV_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \geq r \min \{NV_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}), NV_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{y})\}; \forall \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in \mathbf{U} \quad \text{i.e.} \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \geq \min \{\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}), \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{y})\}; \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \leq \max \{\hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}), \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{y})\}; \left(\inf_{\mathbf{v} \in (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})} \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{v}) \right) \leq \max \{\hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}), \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{y})\}$$

$\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}}$ inequality (2) :

- (i) $NV_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \geq NV_{M_{NV}}(\neg \mathbf{x})$ i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \geq \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\neg \mathbf{x}); \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\neg \mathbf{x}); \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\neg \mathbf{x})$
- (ii) $NV_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \geq NV_{M_{NV}}(\sim \mathbf{x})$ i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \geq \hat{\mathbf{T}}_{M_{NV}}(\sim \mathbf{x}); \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \hat{\mathbf{I}}_{M_{NV}}(\sim \mathbf{x}); \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \hat{\mathbf{F}}_{M_{NV}}(\sim \mathbf{x})$

Here,

- M_{NV} is a non- empty neutrosophic vague set with a single universe \mathbf{U}
- $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NV}}} = (\mathbf{U}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ is a **BZMV^{dm}** – algebraic structure of the underlying single universal set \mathbf{U} of a neutrosophic vague set M_{NV} , with a binary operation \oplus , two unary operations \neg, \sim and a constant $\mathbf{0}$ which satisfies the following **BZMV^{dm}** - axioms: $\forall \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z} \in \mathbf{U}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) & (x \oplus y) \oplus z = (y \oplus z) \oplus x & (2) & (x \oplus 0) = x & (3) & \neg (\neg x) = x \\
 (4) & \neg (\neg x \oplus y) \oplus y = \neg (x \oplus \neg y) \oplus x & (5) & \sim x \oplus \sim \sim x = \neg 0 & (6) & x \oplus \sim \sim u_x = \sim \sim x \\
 (7) & \sim \neg [(\neg (x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y)] = \neg (\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \oplus \neg \sim \sim y
 \end{aligned}$$

4. Neutrosophic Vague Binary BZMV^{dm} Sub - algebra

In this section neutrosophic vague BZMV^{dm} Sub - algebra is extended to its binary concept.

Definition 4.1 (Neutrosophic vague binary BZMV^{dm} Sub - algebra)

A neutrosophic vague binary BZMV^{dm}- subalgebra (NVB BZMV^{dm} Sub-algebra, in short) is a structure $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}} = (\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ with, $\hat{T} = [T^{-1}, T^+]$; $\hat{I} = [I^{-1}, I^+]$; $\hat{F} = [F^{-1}, F^+]$, which satisfies, the following two $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ inequalities:

$\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ inequality (1) :

$$\left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r$$

$\min \{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}; \forall v, x, y \in U$

$\left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(v) \leq \max \{ \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(x), \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(y) \}; \left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(v) \leq \max \{ \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(x), \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(y) \} \right) \right)$

i.e., $\left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} \hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(v) \geq \min \{ \hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(x), \hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(y) \}; \right)$

$\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ inequality (2) :

- (i) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x)$ *i.e.,* $\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq \hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x); \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x); \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x)$
- (ii) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x)$ *i.e.,* $\hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq \hat{T}_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x); \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq \hat{I}_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x); \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq \hat{F}_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x)$

Here,

- M_{NVB} is a non- empty neutrosophic vague binary set with two universes U_1, U_2
- $U^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}} = (U = \{U_1 \cup U_2\}, \oplus, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ is a BZMV^{dm} – algebraic structure of the underlying universal set U which is got by combining the two universes of the given neutrosophic vague binary set M_{NVB} , with a binary operation \oplus , two unary operations \neg, \sim and a constant 0 which satisfies the following BZMV^{dm} - axioms:

$$\forall x, y, z \in U$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (1) & (x \oplus y) \oplus z = (y \oplus z) \oplus x & (2) & (x \oplus 0) = x & (3) & \neg (\neg x) = x \\
 (4) & \neg (\neg x \oplus y) \oplus y = \neg (x \oplus \neg y) \oplus x & (5) & \sim x \oplus \sim \sim x = \neg 0 & (6) & x \oplus \sim \sim x = \sim \sim x \\
 (7) & \sim \neg [(\neg (x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y)] = \neg (\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \oplus \neg \sim \sim y
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4.2

(i) In a NVB BZMV^{dm} – subalgebra, possible operations can also be further derived

$$(1) (x \odot y) = \neg (\neg x \odot \neg y) \quad (2) (x \vee y) = \neg (\neg x \oplus y) \oplus y \quad (3) (x \wedge y) = \neg (\neg (x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y)$$

(ii) In neutrosophic vague binary concept $U=\{U_1 \cup U_2\}$. But in neutrosophic vague it is single universe U

Example 4.3

Let $U_1 = \{0, p, q, 1\}$ and $U_2 = \{0, r, s, 1\}$ be two universes with neutrosophic vague binary membership grades as given below:

$$\forall p \in U_1, NVB_{M_{NVB}}(p) = \{ [0.8, 0.9] | [0.1, 0.6] | [0.1, 0.2]; p = 0 \text{ and } 1; [0.9, 0.9] | [0.1, 0.2] | [0.1, 0.1]; 0 < p < 1 \}; \forall q \in U_2, NVB_{M_{NVB}}(q) = \{ [0.7, 0.9] | [0.2, 0.5] | [0.1, 0.3]; q = 0 \text{ and } 1; [0.8, 0.9] | [0.1, 0.4] | [0.1, 0.2]; 0 < q < 1 \}$$

Corresponding neutrosophic vague binary set (in short, NVBS) is given as below:

$$\therefore \mathbf{M}_{\text{NVB}} = \left\{ \left(\frac{[0.8,0.9][0.1,0.6][0.1,0.2]}{0}, \frac{[0.9,0.9][0.1,0.2][0.1,0.1]}{p}, \frac{[0.9,0.9][0.1,0.2][0.1,0.1]}{q}, \frac{[0.8,0.9][0.1,0.6][0.1,0.2]}{1} \right), \left(\frac{[0.7,0.9][0.2,0.5][0.1,0.3]}{0}, \frac{[0.8,0.9][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.2]}{r}, \frac{[0.8,0.9][0.1,0.4][0.1,0.2]}{s}, \frac{[0.7,0.9][0.2,0.5][0.1,0.3]}{1} \right) \right\}$$

Combined universal set is $\mathbf{U} = \{\mathbf{U}_1 \cup \mathbf{U}_2\} = \{\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{1}\}$ & $\{\mathbf{U}_1 \cap \mathbf{U}_2\} = \{\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}\}$ Neutrosophic vague binary union of common elements are given by,

$$[\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.6}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] \cup [\mathbf{0.7}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.2}, \mathbf{0.5}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.3}] = [\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.5}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\mathbf{0}) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\mathbf{1})$$

Combined neutrosophic vague binary membership grades are given as follows:

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\mathbf{t}) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.5}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{0} \\ [\mathbf{0.9}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.1}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{p} \\ [\mathbf{0.9}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.1}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{q} \\ [\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.4}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{r} \\ [\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.4}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{s} \\ [\mathbf{0.8}, \mathbf{0.9}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.5}][\mathbf{0.1}, \mathbf{0.2}] ; \mathbf{t} = \mathbf{1} \end{array} \right.$$

Algebraic structure $\mathbf{U}^{\mathfrak{M}_{\text{NVB}}} = (\mathbf{U} = \{\mathbf{U}_1 \cap \mathbf{U}_2\}, *, \neg, \sim, \mathbf{0})$ with binary and unary operations defined as in Cayley table given below clearly indicates a **BZMV^{dm}** – subalgebra.

Cayley table for unary operations \neg and \sim are given below:

	0	p	q	r	s	1
\neg	1	r	s	s	r	0
\sim	1	0	0	0	0	0

Cayley table for binary operation ' * ' is given below

*	0	p	q	r	s	1
0	0	p	q	r	s	1
p	p	p	r	r	1	1
q	q	r	s	1	s	1
r	r	r	1	1	1	1
s	s	1	s	1	s	1
1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Now have to verify, neutrosophic vague binary concept! For that check the inequalities given in definition 4.1.

$\mathfrak{M}_{\text{NVB}}$ inequality (1): (Binary Operation)

$$\forall x, y \in U, \left(\inf_{v \in (x * y)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\inf_{v \in \{0, p, q, r, s, 1\}} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(u_v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\text{glb}_{v \in \{0, p, q, r, s, 1\}} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \left(\min_{v \in \{0, p, q, r, s, 1\}} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}$$

$$= \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2] ; v = 0 \\ [0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1] ; v = p \\ [0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1] ; v = q \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2] ; v = r \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2] ; v = s \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2] ; v = 1 \end{array} \right\} = \cap \left\{ \begin{array}{l} [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2] ; v = 0 \\ [0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1] ; v = p \\ [0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1] ; v = q \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2] ; v = r \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2] ; v = s \\ [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2] ; v = 1 \end{array} \right\} = [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]$$

[In neutrosophic concept, minimum concept has been taken as intersection. i.e., in this case, (Min, Max, Max)]

$$\therefore \left(\inf_{v \in (x * y)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) = [0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]$$

In this case, for any pair of elements from U,

$$\left(\inf_{v \in (x \oplus y)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}, \text{ got satisfied.}$$

$\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ inequality (2): (Unary operations)

Next to check, the 2 inequalities of $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ (2) for all elements of U.

(i) From Cayley table for unary operation \neg (Kleene or Zadeh or fuzzy orthocomplementation)

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x) ; \forall x \in U \text{ as showed in table.}$$

u_x	$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x)$	$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x)$
0	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
u_p	[0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]
u_q	[0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]
u_r	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]
u_s	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]
1	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]

(ii) From Cayley table for unary operation \sim (Brower orthocomplementation)

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x) ; \forall x \in U \text{ as showed in table}$$

x	$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x)$	$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x)$
0	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
p	[0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
q	[0.9, 0.9][0.1, 0.2][0.1, 0.1]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
r	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
s	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.4][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]
1	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]	[0.8, 0.9][0.1, 0.5][0.1, 0.2]

So given example is a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ with structure $(U^{\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}}, *, \neg, \sim, 0)$

Remark 4.4

It is to be noted that,

(i) first column of the Cayley table for binary operation will be a copy of column of operands, using definition 2.8 (BZMV2) (ii)

last row and column of the Cayley table for binary operation will be always 1 for a $BZMV^{dM}$ – algebra, by using (3) and (4) of theorem 2.12

Theorem 4.5

If M_{NVB} is a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ then the following results are true:

(1) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus y) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \oplus x)$ [i. e., commutative law holds for Binary Operation]

(2) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \oplus z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus (y \oplus z))$

[i. e., associative law holds for Binary Operation]

(3) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus 1) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1)$

(4) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus \neg x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1)$

[neutrosophic vague binary membership grade of an element binary operated with it's kleene complement] (5)
 always produce the neutrosophic vague binary membership grade of the maximum element 1

$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg(x \oplus \sim \sim x) \oplus \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1)$

(6) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg x \oplus \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1)$

(7) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x)$

(8) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x)$

(9) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \vee \sim y)$

(10) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim(x \vee y)) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \wedge \sim y)$ (Equivalently, $x \leq y$)

implies $\sim y \leq \sim x$)

(11) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$

(12) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x)$

(13) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \oplus \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x)$

(14) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0)$

Proof

$$(1) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y}) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y}) \oplus \mathbf{0}),$$

by putting $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y})$ in definition 4.1 (2), $(\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{x}$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{y} \oplus \mathbf{0}) \oplus \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{y} \oplus \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (2)}$$

$$(2) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{y}) \oplus \mathbf{z}) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{y} \oplus \mathbf{z}) \oplus \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus (\mathbf{y} \oplus \mathbf{z})), \text{ by using theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$(3) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{1}) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{0}), \text{ since } \mathbf{1} = \neg \mathbf{0}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus (\sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x})), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (5)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using theorem 4.1 (6)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \mathbf{0}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (5)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{1}), \text{ since } \neg \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{1}$$

$$(4) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{x})$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \neg \mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (3)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\neg \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{0}) \oplus \neg \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (2)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\mathbf{0} \oplus \neg \mathbf{x}) \oplus \neg \mathbf{x}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{0}) \oplus \neg \mathbf{0}), \text{ by theorem 4.1 (4)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{1}) \oplus \mathbf{1}), \text{ since } \neg \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{1}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \mathbf{0})$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{1}), \text{ since } \neg \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{1}$$

$$(5) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x})$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (6)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \neg (\sim \sim \mathbf{x})), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{1}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (4)}$$

$$(6) \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \mathbf{x} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x})$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \mathbf{x} \oplus (\mathbf{u}_x \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x})), \text{ by using definition 4.1(6)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\neg \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (2)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{x}) \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{1} \oplus \sim \sim \mathbf{x}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (4)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{1}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{1}), \text{ by putting } \mathbf{x} = \sim \sim \mathbf{x} \text{ in theorem 4.5 (3)}$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\mathbf{x} \wedge \sim \sim \mathbf{x})$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x}))$$

=

[From remark 4.2 (i) 3, we have, $(\mathbf{x} \wedge \mathbf{y}) = \neg (\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \mathbf{y}) \oplus \neg \mathbf{y})$, by putting $\mathbf{y} = \sim \sim \mathbf{x}$]

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\neg (\neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x} \oplus \mathbf{x}) \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x}))$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\neg (\mathbf{x} \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x}) \oplus \neg \sim \sim \mathbf{x}))$$

(7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg(x \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \oplus \sim \sim x)) \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg(x \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \oplus x)) \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg(x \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \oplus x)) \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg(\neg x \oplus \sim \sim x) \oplus \sim \sim x))
 \end{aligned}$$

[From definition 4.1(4), $\neg(\neg x \oplus y) \oplus y = \neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus x$]

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg \mathbf{1} \oplus \sim \sim x)), \text{ by definition 4.5 (6)} \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\mathbf{0} \oplus \sim \sim x)), \text{ since } \neg \mathbf{1} = \mathbf{0} \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \mathbf{0})), \text{ from theorem 4.5 (1)} \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x)), \text{ from theorem 4.1 (1)} \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x), \text{ since } \neg(\sim \sim x) = \sim \sim \sim x \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(x), \text{ since } \sim \sim \sim x = x
 \end{aligned}$$

(8) Consider definition 4.1 (7),

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \oplus \neg \sim \sim y)$$

By putting $y = x$ in the above,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg(x \oplus \neg x) \oplus \neg x]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \oplus \neg \sim \sim x), \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg \mathbf{1} \oplus \neg x]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \mathbf{1} \oplus \neg \sim \sim x), \text{ by using definition 4.5 (4)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\mathbf{0} \oplus \neg x]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\mathbf{0} \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg x \oplus \mathbf{0}]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \sim \sim x \oplus \mathbf{0}), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg x]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \sim \sim x), \text{ by definition 4.1 (2)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \sim \sim x), \text{ by definition 4.1 (3)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \neg \sim \sim x), \text{ by applying } \neg \text{ on both sides.} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \sim x), \text{ by using definition 4.1(3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

(9) Consider definition 4.1 (7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim \neg[\neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y]) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \oplus \neg \sim \sim y) \quad \Rightarrow \\
 &\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg \sim x \oplus \neg \neg \sim y) \oplus \neg \neg \sim y) \text{ [By using auxiliary operation, } (x \wedge y) = \\
 &\neg[\neg(x \oplus \neg y) \oplus \neg y] \text{] \& [By using theorem 4.1 (8), } \neg \sim x = \sim \sim x \text{]} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\sim \sim x \oplus \sim y) \oplus \sim y), \text{ by using definition 4.1 (3)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg(\neg \sim x \oplus \sim y) \oplus \sim y), \text{ by using } \sim \sim x = \neg \sim x \quad \Rightarrow \\
 &\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x \vee \sim y) \\
 &\quad \text{[By using auxiliary operation, } \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(x \vee y) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\neg[\neg(x \oplus y) \oplus y]) \text{]}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$(10) \text{ Let } \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(y) \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(x \wedge y) \quad \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim(x \wedge y)), \text{ by applying } \sim \text{ on both sides and by using (9)} \quad \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x \vee \sim y), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (9)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim y) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{MNVB}}(\sim x)$$

Using theorem 4.5 (7), $\forall x, NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x)$.

So now the contraposition law is equivalent to the de Morgan law:

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim (x \vee y)) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \wedge \sim y)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (11) \quad & NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge \sim x) \\ &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg(x \oplus \neg \sim x) \oplus \neg \sim x)) \\ &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg(x \oplus \sim \sim x) \oplus \sim \sim x)), \text{ by theorem 2.12 (8) \& by definition 4.5 (8)} \\ &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 1), \text{ by definition 4.5 (5)} \\ &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0) \end{aligned}$$

$$(12) \text{ From definition 4.5 (8), } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x)$$

Put $x = \sim x$, in the above then, $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x)$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg \neg \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x), \text{ since } \sim \sim x = \neg \sim x$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x), \text{ since } \neg \neg \sim x = \sim x$$

$$(13) \quad NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x), \text{ by definition 4.1 (6)}$$

Taking Brouwerian orthocomplementation to both sides,

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \wedge \sim \sim \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim \sim x)$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x \wedge \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x) \text{ [By theorem 4.5(12), } \sim \sim \sim x = \sim x]$$

$$(14) \text{ To prove that, } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0).$$

It is enough to prove that,

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0)$$

$$\leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0) \text{ and } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0)$$

We know that, $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0)$

$\forall x \in M_{NVB}$, where M_{NVB} is a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$,

$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1)$, since 1 is the maximum element;

$$\text{In particular, } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(1) \Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0)$$

Similarly, being the least element,

$\forall x \in M_{NVB}$, where M_{NVB} is a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$,

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0)$$

In

$$\text{particular, } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg 0) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim 0)$$

Theorem 4.6

Let

M_{NVB} is a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$. Then

$$(i) \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}, NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge y) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim x)$$

$$\text{Equivalently, } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge y) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim y)$$

$$(ii) \text{ Let } x \in M_{NVB} \text{ be such that } NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x),$$

$$\text{Then } \forall y \in M_{NVB}, NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge y) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg y)$$

Proof

$$(i) \text{ Assume } (x \wedge y) = 0$$

Now,

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}((y \wedge \sim x) \vee 0), \text{ since in any lattice } (x \vee 0) = x$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge \sim x) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}((y \wedge \sim x) \vee (y \wedge \sim y)), \text{ by a result } (y \wedge \sim y) = 0, \text{ of BZMV}^{dM} \text{ algebra}$$

$$= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge (\sim x \vee \sim y)), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (9)}$$

$$= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge \sim (x \wedge y)), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (9)}$$

$$= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge \sim 0), \text{ by assumption}$$

$$= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y),$$

$$= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge 1), \text{ since } \sim 0 = \neg 0 = 1$$

$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y)$, [since in any lattice $(y \wedge 1) = y \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y \wedge 1) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y)$]
 $\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x)$
 Conversely, suppose $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x) \Rightarrow$
 then $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge y)$ =
 $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge (y \wedge \sim x))$ =
 $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y \wedge (x \wedge \sim x))$, by associativity
 $= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y \wedge 0)$, by theorem 4.5 (11)
 $= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0)$, since in any lattice $(y \wedge 0) = y$
 Equivalently, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge y) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0) \Leftrightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim y)$, can be proved
 (ii) Suppose $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \oplus x)$.
 Then, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \odot x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge y)$.
 Thus we got, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg y)$ iff $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge y) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0)$

Theorem 4.7

In a $\mathfrak{M}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}$ the following holds :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) &= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) \Leftrightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x \oplus x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(1) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \oplus x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) \end{aligned}$$

Proof

Assume $\sim \sim x = u_x$. Then, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Definition 4.1 (6)} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \oplus \sim \sim x) &= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) \\ &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \oplus x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again, from definition 4.1 (5)} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x \oplus \sim \sim x) &= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg 0) \\ &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x \oplus x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(1) \end{aligned}$$

Assume, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(u_x \oplus u_x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x)$. Then by theorem 4.6 (ii), since $\neg x \in \mathfrak{M}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}$ and

$$(u_x \wedge \neg u_x) = 0 \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge \neg x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0) \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \sim x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x), \text{ by putting } x = \sim x$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x)$$

condition $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim x \oplus x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(1)$, it is clear that,

$$\sim \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x) \leq \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x).$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge \sim \sim x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg [\neg (x \oplus \neg \sim \sim x) \oplus \neg \sim \sim x])$$

[Using definition of \wedge]

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg [\neg (x \oplus \neg \neg \sim x) \oplus \neg \neg \sim x]), \text{ [since } \neg \sim x = \sim \sim x]$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg [\neg (x \oplus \sim x) \oplus \sim x]), \text{ [since } \neg \neg x = x]$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (0 \oplus \sim x))$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg (\sim x \oplus 0)), \text{ by theorem 4.5 (1)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\neg \sim x), \text{ by definition 4.1 (2)}$$

$$= \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x). \text{ [since } \neg \sim u_x = \sim \sim x]$$

Similarly, we get, $\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(\sim \sim x)$. Hence proved.

Theorem 4.8

Let M_{NVB} be a $\mathfrak{M}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}$; then for any $x, y, z \in \text{M}_{\text{NVB}}$,

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}((x \oplus y) \wedge z) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0) \text{ iff } \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(x \wedge z) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0) \text{ and}$$

$$\text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(y \wedge z) = \text{NVB}_{\text{M}_{\text{NVB}}}(0)$$

Proof

Suppose, $NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$
 $\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge z) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$ and $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge z) \leq NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$, by theorem 4.6
 $\Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge z)$, trivial
 Conversely, let $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$ and $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$.
 $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \wedge \neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y \wedge \neg z)$.
 So, $NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \oplus \neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus (y \oplus \neg z))$, by definition 4.5 (2)
 $= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \oplus \neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg z)$, from assumption
 $\therefore NVB_{M_{NVB}}((x \oplus y) \wedge z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg [\neg(x \oplus \neg z) \oplus \neg \neg z]) =$
 $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(((x \oplus y) \oplus \neg z) \odot \neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0 \odot \neg z) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x \odot 0) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(0)$

5. Ideals in Neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ sub-algebra

Concept of ideal with three different kinds are developed in this section

Definition 5.1 (NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ - ideal)

Let M_{NVB} be a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ and I_{NVB} be a nonempty subset of M_{NVB} . Then I_{NVB} is a neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ - ideal (NVB – $BZMV^{dM}$ ideal) if the following inequalities got satisfied:

- (i) $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(0) \geq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x) ; \forall x \in I_{NVB}$
- (ii) $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \oplus y) \geq r \min \{NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{I_{NVB}}(y)\} ; \forall x, y \in I_{NVB}$
- (iii) $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(y) \geq r \min \{NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{I_{NVB}}(y \leq x)\} ; \forall x, y \in I_{NVB}$

Definition 5.2 (prime ideal, ~ ideal, normal ideal of a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra)

Let M_{NVB} be a $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$ and I_{NVB} be a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ - ideal of M_{NVB} . I_{NVB} is called,

- (i) a neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ - prime ideal (NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ – prime ideal) of M_{NVB}
 $\Leftrightarrow \{NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \odot \neg y) \in M_{NVB} \text{ or } NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \in M_{NVB} ; \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$
- (ii) a neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ ~ ideal (NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ ~ ideal) of M_{NVB} if it satisfies:
 $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim \sim x \odot \sim \neg y \in I_{NVB}) \geq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \odot y) ; \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$
- (iii) a neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ normal ideal (NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ normal ideal) of M_{NVB} whenever
 $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \geq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot y)$ and $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \leq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot y)$
 i.e., $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot y), \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$

Theorem 5.3

I_{NVB}

is a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ – p ideal of $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}} \Leftrightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x) \geq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \wedge y) \\ \text{or} \\ NVB_{I_{NVB}}(y) \geq NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \wedge y) \end{array} \right\}$

Proof

Assume I_{NVB} is a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ – p ideal of $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{NVB}}$

$$\Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \odot \neg y) \geq r \min \{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\} ; \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \\ \text{or} \\ NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \geq r \min \{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\} ; \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \end{array} \right.$$

Without loss of generality, consider $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \geq r \min \{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(x), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(y)\}$

$$NVB_{I_{NVB}}(x \wedge y)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (y \wedge x) \text{ [using commutativity of } \wedge \text{]} && = \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (y \odot (x \oplus \neg y)) \text{ [by using } (a \wedge b) = a \odot (b \oplus \neg a) \text{]} && = \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus \neg (x \oplus \neg y))) \text{ [by using } (a \odot b) = \neg (\neg a \oplus \neg b) \text{]} && = \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus \neg (\neg y \oplus x))) \text{ [by commutativity of } \oplus \text{]} && = \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus \neg (\neg y \oplus \neg \neg x))) \text{ [since } \neg \neg x = x \text{]} \\
 &= \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus (y \odot \neg x))) \text{ [since } \neg (\neg y \oplus \neg \neg x) = (y \odot \neg x) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{]} \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus (y \odot \neg x))) \geq \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (x \wedge y) \text{ and} \\
 &\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x \odot y) \geq r \min \{ \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (x), \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (y) \} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus (y \odot \neg x)) \oplus (\neg x \odot y)) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\neg y \oplus (y \odot \neg x)) \oplus (y \odot \neg x)) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\text{Hence, } \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (y \vee (y \odot \neg x)) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (y) \in I_{\text{NVB}}, \text{ since } (y \odot \neg x) \leq y \\
 &\therefore \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (y) \geq \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x \odot y) \\
 &\text{Similarly, if } \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg y \odot x) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (x) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (x) \geq \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg y \odot x) \\
 &\text{Conversely, } \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} ((\neg x \odot y) \wedge (x \odot \neg y)) = \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (0) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ [from definition of NVB BZMV}^{dM} \text{ ideal]} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ or } \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (x \odot \neg y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\Rightarrow I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ is a NVB BZMV}^{dM} \text{ prime ideal of } \mathfrak{M}_{M_{\text{NVB}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.4

Let I_{NVB} be an NVB ideal of a neutrosophic vague binary BZMV^{dM} – subalgebra $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{\text{NVB}}}$ and $\sim \sim x = x$ for all $x \in M_{\text{NVB}}$. Then the following conditions are equivalent :

- (1) I_{NVB} is a NVB BZMV^{dM} normal ideal
- (2) I_{NVB} is a NVB BZMV^{dM} \sim ideal
- (3) $\text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim x) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Leftrightarrow \text{NVB}_{I_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x) \in I_{\text{NVB}}$

Proof

(1) \Rightarrow (2)

Let I_{NVB} is a NVB BZMV^{dM}- normal ideal of $\mathfrak{M}_{M_{\text{NVB}}}$

Then, $\forall x, y \in M_{\text{NVB}}, \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg \neg x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ [by using } x = \neg \neg x \text{]} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \neg x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ [by property of BZMV}^{dM} \text{ – subalgebra } \neg \neg x = \sim \neg x \text{]} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \neg x \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ [since given } \sim \sim x = x \text{]} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \sim y \odot \sim \neg x) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \text{ [by commutativity]} \\
 &\therefore \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \sim y \odot \sim \neg x) \geq \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (x \odot y), \forall x, y \in M_{\text{NVB}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow I_{\text{NVB}}$ is a neutrosophic vague binary BZMV^{dM} \sim ideal of M_{NVB} [by definition 5.2 (ii)]

(2) \Rightarrow (1)

Let I_{NVB} be a neutrosophic vague binary BZMV^{dM} \sim ideal.

Then, $\forall x, y \in M_{\text{NVB}}, \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow$

$\text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \neg (\neg x) \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim (\neg \neg x) \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \neg (\sim x) \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim (\neg \sim x) \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\sim \sim \sim x \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}}, \text{ since } [\neg \sim x = \sim \sim x] \\
 &\Rightarrow \text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg (\sim \sim x) \odot \sim \sim y) \in I_{\text{NVB}} \Rightarrow
 \end{aligned}$$

$\text{NVB}_{M_{\text{NVB}}} (\neg x \odot y) \in I_{\text{NVB}}$, so I_{NVB} is a NVB BZMV^{dM} normal ideal of M_{NVB} .

(1) \Rightarrow (3)

Let I_{NVB} be a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ normal ideal of M_{NVB}

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot y), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot 1) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot 1), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \text{ [by putting } y = 1\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\neg x \oplus \neg 1)) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\sim x \oplus \neg 1)), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \text{ [by definition of } \odot\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\neg x \oplus 0)) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\sim x \oplus 0)), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\neg x)) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\sim x)), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \text{ [since } (x \oplus 0) = x\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg\neg(\neg x)) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg\neg(\sim x)), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x) \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x), \quad \forall x, y \in M_{NVB} \text{ [since } \neg\neg(x) = x\text{]}$$

(3) \Rightarrow (1)

Suppose, $NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x) \in I_{NVB} \Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x) \in I_{NVB}$

$$NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot y) \in I_{NVB}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\sim x \odot \sim\sim y) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [since } y = \sim\sim y, \text{ by definition]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\neg\sim x \oplus \neg y)) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [by definition of } \odot\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(\sim\sim x \oplus \neg y)) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [}\neg\sim x = \sim\sim x\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(x \oplus \sim y)) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [given } \sim\sim x = x\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg(x \odot \neg\sim y)) \in I_{NVB}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot \neg\sim y) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [by property of } \odot\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot \sim\sim y) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [}\neg\sim y = \sim\sim y\text{]}$$

$$\Rightarrow NVB_{I_{NVB}}(\neg x \odot y) \in I_{NVB} \text{ [by using the given property } \sim\sim x = x\text{]}$$

$\therefore I_{NVB}$ is a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ ideal

6. Direct sum of neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra

In this section, a method is provided as a theorem to obtain a NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ Sub -algebra by joining two NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ Sub -algebras having $\{0, 1\}$ as common elements.

Theorem 6.1

Let $\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB} = \langle U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}}, \oplus_1, \neg_1, \sim_1, 0, 1 \rangle$ and $\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB} = \langle U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}}, \oplus_2, \neg_2, \sim_2, 0, 1 \rangle$ be two NVB $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebras such that $(U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}} \cap U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}}) = \{0, 1\}$. Let $U^{\mathfrak{M}_{WNVB}} = (U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}} \cup U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}})$ and let a binary operation \ominus be defined on Z as follows:

$$(a \ominus b) = \begin{cases} a \oplus_1 b & \text{if } a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}} \\ a \oplus_2 b & \text{if } a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}} \\ a & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\neg^{\ominus} a = \begin{cases} \neg_1 a & \text{if } a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}} \\ \neg_2 a & \text{if } a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}} \end{cases}$$

$$\sim^{\ominus} a = \begin{cases} \sim_1 a & \text{if } a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}} \\ \sim_2 a & \text{if } a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}} \end{cases}$$

Then, $\langle U^{\mathfrak{M}_{WNVB}}, \ominus, \neg^{\ominus}, \sim^{\ominus}, 0, 1 \rangle$ is a neutrosophic vague binary $BZMV^{dM}$ – subalgebra \mathfrak{M}_{ZNVB} .

Here, \ominus denotes direct sum.

Proof

(1) Let $a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{MNVB}}$ and $c \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{PNVB}}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 NVB_{M_{NVB}}((a \oplus b) \oplus c) &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}((a \oplus_1 b) \oplus c) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a \oplus_1 b) \\
 NVB_{M_{NVB}}((b \oplus c) \oplus a) &= NVB_{M_{NVB}}(b \oplus a) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a \oplus b) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a \oplus_1 b)
 \end{aligned}$$

(2) Let $a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}}$ and $0 \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}$

$$NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a \oplus 0) = NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a)$$

Similarly, all the axioms for a $BZMV^{dM}$ -subalgebra can be verified

Case (i) : $a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}}, (\forall a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}})$ (1)

$$\left(\inf_{v \in (a \oplus b)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) = \left(\inf_{v \in (a \oplus_1 b)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(b)\} \tag{2}$$

$(\forall a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}})$

(i) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg^{\odot} a) \Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg_1 a)$

(ii) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim^{\odot} a) \Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim_1 a)$

[Since, $\langle U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}}, \oplus_1, \neg_1, \sim_1, 0, 1 \rangle$ is a $NVB BZMV^{dM}$ -subalgebra]

Case (ii) : $a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}, (\forall a, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}})$

$$(1) \left(\inf_{v \in (a \oplus b)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) = \left(\inf_{v \in (a \oplus_2 b)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(b)\}$$

(2) $(\forall a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}})$

(i) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg^{\odot} a) \Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\neg_2 a)$

(ii) $NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim^{\odot} a) \Rightarrow NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a) \geq NVB_{M_{NVB}}(\sim_2 a)$

[Since, $\langle U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}, \oplus_2, \neg_2, \sim_2, 0, 1 \rangle$ is a $NVB BZMV^{dM}$ -subalgebra]

Case (iii) : $\forall a \in U^{\dagger}, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}$ or $a \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}, b \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}}$

(1) $(\forall x \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}}, y \in U^{\ddagger}$ or $x \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{P_{NVB}}}, y \in U^{\mathfrak{M}_{NVB}})$

$$\left(\inf_{v \in (a \oplus b)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) = \left(\inf_{v \in (a)} NVB_{M_{NVB}}(v) \right) \geq r \min\{NVB_{M_{NVB}}(a), NVB_{M_{NVB}}(b)\}$$

Being a unary operation, 2nd axiom does not exists.

Clearly all the conditions for a $NVB BZMV^{dM}$ -subalgebra is verified. It is clear that combining of two $NVB BZMV^{dM}$ -subalgebras, will produce the same.

7. Conclusions

Binary concept leads us to handle the situations with two universal sets which are found to be common in real-life. In this paper neutrosophic vague binary **BZMV^{dM}** Sub-algebra of **BZMV^{dM}**-algebra is developed. This idea will provide a combined effect of the distributive Brouwer Zadeh lattice with Many -Valued or Multi - Valued algebra when stipulated into the de-Morgan’s zone. Its basic-ideal with various sub kinds are also developed. Some theorems, properties, direct sum for this new concept are explored. This paper is an attempt to discuss with mixed patterns and an investigation towards its wide scope. It could be further extended to higher dimensions. Pre-**BZMV^{dM}** algebraic structure is a weaker structure than **BZMV^{dM}**-algebra. In some times, violation of theorems in stronger structure may come into a control mode in their relaxed forms. That also could be verified by comparing both these structures. **BZMV^{dM}**-algebra can be considered as a strong **MV**- algebraic structure in de- Morgan’s environment. Same way, one more strengthened **MV**- algebraic structure namely neutrosophic vague binary - **BZMV_Δ(NVB – BZMV_Δ – subalgebra)** can also be developed. Here Δ is an additional unary operator in the context. It can be also extended towards the de – Morgans atmosphere and can get a more tightened structure neutrosophic vague binary **BZMV_Δ^{dM}** Sub-algebra of **BZMV_Δ^{dM}**- algebra (**NVB BZMV_Δ^{dM} Sub – algebra of BZMV_Δ^{dM} – algebra**). In future, its applications can be extended to a number of areas like geology, unmanned aerial vehicle, business analysis, chemistry, mechatronics, aerospace, biomedical etc and have to be discussed in detail. Numerous applications can be tried out in the field of working algorithms of

vacuum cleaners, washing machines etc, and in stock trading, medical diagnosis and treatment plans, weather forecasting systems, 3D animations etc. Neutrosophic Vague Binary ideas with its logical **BZMV^{dm}** Sub - algebraic pattern can be hopefully developed towards this area and to its working algorithms to produce more accuracy in this digital world.

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